

THE IMPACT OF OVERTOURISM ON THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY OF TOURIST DESTINATIONS

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Abstract: Studying the behaviour of the consumer of tourist products and services has been and will remain a challenge, given that a multitude of diverse influencing factors impact it continuously, which, in addition to heterogeneous behaviours that exert pressure on the adaptation capacity of the tourist service offer, has a significant impact on the community, in particular, as well as on the environment, in general.

Consequently, the phenomenon of overtourism tends to expand alarmingly on the most visited tourist destinations globally. Finding solutions to prevent the negative effects and hostile attitudes generated by this phenomenon has become a major concern for local communities and for international organizations.

This paper thus aims to explain, on the one hand, the particularities of consumer behaviour of tourist products and services in the contemporary era, and on the other hand, it aims to analyse the phenomenon of overtourism using information from secondary data sources, which allow for the outline of a comprehensive and complex picture of this phenomenon. The overarching purpose of the approach is to identify strategies for sustainable tourism development so as to minimize the costs brought about by this phenomenon on the population and the Planet.

Keywords: tourist behaviour, impact of overtourism, sustainable development strategies, destination management

JEL classification: M31, Q10

1. Introduction

The study of tourism consumer behaviour starts from the premise that, in the contemporary era, as a result of the unprecedented development of information technology, as well as of communication tools with actual and potential consumers, the tourist is increasingly better informed, their needs and expectations are continuously diversified. Thus, the tourism industry is facing an unprecedented pressure as a result of the pressing need to know who, how, when, why and under the action of which factors purchasing decisions are made, in order to come up with offers adapted to consumer needs, without jeopardizing the interests and lifestyle of local residents and without irreparably disturbing the balance of the environment.

Having become a field of interest for researchers and academics since the 1960s, the issue of consumer behaviour has been debated in numerous works, starting with Engel et al. (1968) or Howard & Sheth (1969) and continuing with Schiffman & Kanuk (1978) or Solomon (1996).

Seen as a sum of activities that are directly related to acquiring, utilising, and consuming goods and services, as well as the choices made before and after (Engel, Blackwell & Miniard-1995), the investigation of consumer behaviour has been one area of interest for both marketing and tourism.

Introduced in the 1990s as a subject of study in undergraduate, master and doctoral curricula, “traveller behaviour” or “tourist behaviour” continues to arouse the interest of specialists who are trying to develop a complex model of consumer behaviour in tourism, a model that explains the multitude of influences exerted by all the factors that act on the tourist's decision and not just some categories of factors, such as social and psychological factors (Moutinho, 1993). In addition, the analysis of purchase decisions requires a unitary analysis, based on a succession of interrelated stages and not on independent

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phases that can be investigated separately (Mill & Morrison, 2002). At the same time, tourist behaviour presents notable particularities within each phase of the process. Both the influencing factors and the characteristics that influence the tourist image are different in the pre-visit, on-site, and during the post-visit stages (Cohen, Prayag & Moital, 2014). However, regardless of the number and intensity of the influencing factors that act on the decision to purchase a tourist product, the new trends registered on the tourism market and dictated by the changes that have occurred in the behaviour of the contemporary tourist cannot be ignored.

Tourism has always encouraged globalization, promoted multiculturalism and economic development, but in recent years, the so-called phenomenon of “deglobalization” that emphasizes a reduction in economic dependencies between states, as well as an accentuation of nationalist spirit, is becoming increasingly evident (Yousaf, 2024). Thus, the emergence of new segments of tourists who, for political, economic or cultural reasons, choose to limit their options to domestic or culturally similar destinations represents a new trend in the evolution of contemporary tourism, determining notable social changes (Cohen & Cohen, 2019)

Another direction that stands out in the tourism sector, having a considerable influence on the theory of social impact and decisional autonomy, brings into question the opportunity to use “service robots” (Liu et al, 2024), as an alternative that allows tourists to behave more autonomously and feel more comfortable than in the presence of human providers. Considering the real or imaginary impact that social factors, respectively social groups, can exert on individual behaviour (Latane, 1981), the issue of decisional autonomy is discussed in a practical manner, which allows consumers to choose the optimal alternatives based on their own expectations (Wertenbroch et al, 2020).

However, the most visible trend that has typified the tourism market in the last decade is the accentuation of the phenomenon of overtourism.

Considered as the new challenge that tourist destinations must face (Butler, 2018), overtourism can be defined as “the impact of tourism on a destination, or parts thereof, that excessively influences the perceived quality of life of citizens and/or quality of visitors experiences in a negative way” (UNWTO, 2018).

The growing demand for tourism from consumers in developing countries and from a growing number of retirees in developed countries (Chambers, 2009), where there are more and more healthy individuals living longer and having the financial and personal freedom to travel (Samochowicz, Kühne & Frick, 2015), combined with the boom in the use of information technology, which allows consumers to share their opinions and experiences online (Song & Wondirad, 2023) and to use online platforms for reservations and ratings, can be considered determinants of the overtourism phenomenon.

Against this background, finding solutions that allow the tourism sector to increase its contribution both to the economic development of communities and to the intensification of cultural exchange, without affecting the quality of life, environmental health, and the cultural identity of residents within the most frequented tourist destinations, becomes a topic of interest for both researchers and local authorities or international organizations. Thus, notions such as “destination management” understood as the “coordinated management of all the elements that make up a sustainable tourism destination (UNWTO, 2019)”, “sustainable tourism policies”, defined as those proactive instruments that allow minimizing effects and potential negative reactions before they occur (Tosun & Caliskan, 2011) or “quality of life perceptions”, referring to the extent to which excessive tourism undesirably affects communities and their resources (Postma & Schmuecker, 2017) are increasingly becoming concerns for specialists.

2. Characteristics of the behaviour of the consumer of tourism products and services in the contemporary world

The way tourists make purchasing decisions, the factors that influence their decision-making process, the experiences of the chosen destinations are subjects of interest both for tourists themselves

and for marketing specialists who analyse their behaviour and base their strategies accordingly or for analysts and sociologists concerned with aspects of contemporary life (Pearce, 2005).

The evaluation of alternatives, the acquisition and consumption of tourism products and services involve a multitude of psycho-social processes, as well as the analysis of an impressive number of personal influencing factors and exogenous influencing factors that researchers and managers of service providers should consider (Kozak & Decrop, 2009).

Understanding consumer behaviour in tourism starts from investigating how the tourist makes the decision to purchase the tourism product. In order to achieve this goal, it is essential to analyse the models that underlie consumer behaviour and which, in classical, traditional approaches, start from the premise that we are dealing with a rational consumer (Mathieson & Wall, 1982). These models are practically based on the analysis of the causal relationship that occurs between variables, namely on measuring the degree to which the change in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variable (Smallman & More, 2010).

Starting from the classical model of consumer behaviour that involves the analysis of three distinct phases: pre-purchase, consumption, and post-purchase (Engel, Blackwell & Miniard, 1995), studying tourist behaviour highlights a series of particularities that must be analysed within each stage of the decision-making process, namely:

- During the first stage, the pre-purchase stage, potential tourists become aware of the need and identify the reasons or motives for going on holiday. They search for information about different destinations and evaluate the alternatives offered by the market to choose the optimal option (Kozak & Decrop, 2009). The decision to take a vacation and the locations chosen are influenced by a number of supply and demand factors, such as demographic, geographic, political, social, economic, and psychological aspects (Crompton & Ankomah, 1993).
- Travellers experience the location, the goods, and services during the second phase. This stage is made up of a number of activities or events that assist customers in giving their decisions and behaviours significance and symbolic worth (Smith, 2003; Uriely, 2005). Customers' experiences are highly subjective and heavily influenced by their feelings, emotions, and social interactions. It entails engaging in activities that lead to learning or knowledge acquisition.
- In the final phase, following their consumption of the tourism product or service, travellers assess their experiences by contrasting the perceived performance with data gathered from a variety of sources, including personal (friends, family) and public (mass media) sources, as well as with their own expectations (Pizam, Neumann & Reichel, 1978). Post-purchase evaluation usually leads to the satisfaction, increased satisfaction or dissatisfaction, results that are considered to be determinants of intentions to return or change domestic or international destinations and which also have a major impact in promoting the favourable or unfavourable aspects of the perceived experiences (Baker & Crompton, 2000).

Many of the classic models that analyse consumer behaviour are criticized by some specialists. Due to the particular circumstances in which travel decisions are made, the primary contention is that these models are unable to adequately represent the complexity of the tourist decision-making process (Hyde & Lawson, 2003). Making travel decisions requires making several decisions about the various components of the vacation schedule, which adds complexity (Decrop & Snelders, 2004), which are produced at the location, while others are made prior to arrival (Choi et al., 2012). Furthermore, group decisions—which have been shown to be incredibly prevalent in the tourism industry—are not taken into consideration by these models (Bronner & de Hoog, 2008). The complexity of choosing to buy tourism-related goods and services is further supported by the fact that situational factors have a significant impact on many travel decisions (March & Woodside, 2005).

It is also important to note that there are a number of behavioural aspects that are thought to be crucial and that significantly distinguish the behaviour of tourists from that of consumers (Pearce, 2005). The extended stages that define visitor behaviour are one of these significant distinctions (Clawson & Knetsch, 1966):

1. unlike scheduled purchases, which are repetitive and typically target everyday goods, many tourists plan and envision their future trip months or even years in advance during the anticipation or pre-purchase phase. Eventually, these decisions may resemble unscheduled ones, which involve the acquisition of goods of higher value and utility.
2. the literature on consumer behaviour does not typically address both the journey to the destination and the journey back. However, the necessity of getting to the destination increases the anticipatory aspects of tourist visits, and these journeys are frequently an essential component of the overall experience. The pre- and post-life stages are also significant subcomponents of the overall costs that visitors must pay to access the on-site experience, as seen from an economic standpoint.
3. while there are undoubtedly other services (like financial-banking or educational services) that are examined in the literature in relation to consumer behaviour, the intensely personal responses and occasionally socio-environmental effects of visitors' actions on-site are unique.
4. lastly, the thinking back stage of the travel experience is frequently prolonged. People reflect on their travel experiences for a month, two, or even years after they have been to the place. In this way, the experience does not deteriorate, and it may even be improved by revisiting the location or by continuously accumulating knowledge about it. The emphasis on experience in tourism aligns with the experience economy concept's more comprehensive approach (Pine & Gilmour, 1999). Certainly, tourism consumers frequently tell stories about their travels, re-examine photographs, organize group meetings and write about their previous experiences (Yagi, 2001). Although research on consumer behaviour has made significant strides in comprehending the idea of satisfaction, there is little and gradually waning interest in considering the long-term impact on an individual's quality of life for many purchased products.

Another characteristic of the behaviour of the consumer of tourism products and services that is worth mentioning is the one related to the interdependence between tourism decisions and other consumption decisions (Woodside et al., 2006; Dolnicar et al., 2008). In the current economic context, when the uncertainties caused by the economic and political crisis leave their mark on the consumer's discretionary income, it is imperative to analyse how consumers decide to spend their income and how these decisions affect the behaviour of the tourism consumer.

Numerous issues with traditional tourism growth models have arisen over time, including unsustainable tourism levels, tourist gentrification, excessive pollution, and social and economic inequality, which have hampered long-term development possibilities (Fletcher et al., 2021; Mowforth & Munt, 2016). Destinations have experienced severe social and ecological repercussions from this conventional paradigm of tourism growth, including environmental degradation, cultural upheaval, and income inequality in emerging nations (Fang et al., 2021), waste production, environmental deterioration, and gentrification of the tourism industry (Blazquez et al., 2019; Creaco & Querini, 2003; Lakshmi & Shaji, 2016).

While the topic of sustainable tourism has been a focus of experts' research since the 1990s, Horne (1992) encouraged the growth of the role of the traveler who values the history and culture of the destinations they visit, whereas Swarbrooke (1999) listed the fundamental obligations of travellers as well as the extra duties of eco-friendly travellers (Table 1).

Table 1: Tourists' responsibilities

Tourists in general	Sustainable tourists
to respect local rules; to abstain from widely denounced, but lawful, actions; to respect religious convictions; not to abuse resources or harm the environment.	And additionally avoid going to a location with a bad human rights record; be accountable for learning about the location, including some of the local language; interact and make friends with locals; to prevent the spread of illness;

	to support the local economy; to boycott companies that underpay their employees.
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Source: Swarbrooke, J. (1999) *Sustainable Tourism*. Wallingford. CABI.

Since more people have realised the link between pandemics, climate change, and travel, the COVID-19 pandemic has increased awareness of environmental issues worldwide (Severo et al., 2021), which has changed demand for eco-friendly travel (Galvani et al., 2020; O'Connor & Assaker, 2021). People are starting to realise that climate change and mental and physical health are related (Marazziti et al., 2021). Cleaner seas and reduced carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions are the results of the COVID-19 travel limitations, which have given the world a respite from overtourism and time to recuperate. Therefore, several specialists have come to the conclusion that one of the direct causes of environmental issues is tourism (O'Connor & Assaker, 2021).

According to the definition of the "new normal" in the post-Covid era, the corporate environment has undergone significant transformation (Prayag, 2023). In order to meet the evolving needs and demands of travellers and to guarantee the sustainability of tourism development from an economic, social, and environmental perspective, tourism in the post-pandemic era has necessitated significant innovation and adaptation of tourism products, services, and policies (Gowreesunkar et al., 2021; Hall et al., 2020). The global economy is in fact undergoing a significant transformation, propelled by supply-side technology innovation. From the standpoint of demand, the new normal suggests a need for, among other things, flexible and small-group travel, special interest tourism, and increased health and hygiene regulations (Prayag, 2023). The sustainability of the global tourist industry has also been impacted by this shift in the supply and demand for tourism-related goods (Buhalis, 2000).

3. Secondary sources analysis of the phenomenon of overtourism and the need to implement effective strategies for the sustainable management of tourist destinations

Starting with the late 20th and early 21st centuries, the impact of tourism has been frequently analysed through three pillars: economic, sociocultural, and environmental (Zemla & Szromek, 2018). Thus, the development of sustainable tourism has been possible by balancing positive and negative effects, with economic benefits and environmental threats usually being weighed against each other (Hunter, 1997).

In the aftermath of the economic crisis of 2008, tourism has been seen as an important economic engine that promotes the development of nations. As a result, many measures have been taken to develop tourism in cities and rural areas. However, these efforts have led to popular holiday destinations, capitals and historical cities, as well as natural attractions, being increasingly affected by overcrowding. Although the phenomenon has existed for some time, with authors such as Jungk (1980) and Krippendorf (1986) addressing this issue in the 1980s, the term "overtourism" has gained increasing attention since 2017, when local perceptions of tourism changed radically, with citizens taking to the streets to protest because they felt pushed out of their cities and overwhelmed by the influx of visitors (Goodwin, 2017).

Defined as uncontrolled and unsustainable tourism, which can generate significant problems when not managed correctly, having the potential to cause much damage and disruption (Coldwell, 2017), overtourism has captured the attention of an increasing number of specialists in recent years.

Although the benefits of tourism are visible in terms of economic growth, contribution to GDP, and social impact, through the creation of new jobs, as well as in terms of better territorial planning (Celik & Cevirgen, 2024), the negative aspects, such as pollution, price increases and the emergence of social conflicts generated cannot be ignored (Baltaci & Cevirgen, 2020; Celik & Cevirgen, 2021; Roberts et al., 2022).

Considered to be one of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the contribution of tourism to GDP (indicator 8.9.1) was 9.1% of global GDP in 2023, representing an increase of 23.2% compared to 2022 and only 4.1% below the level of 2019. At the same time, the number of jobs generated by

tourism activity (indicator 12b) in 2023 was 27 million new jobs, representing an increase of 9.1% compared to 2022 and only 1.4% below the level of 2019 (WTTC, 2024). According to international statistics, the number of international tourist arrivals was 1,304.56 million tourists in 2023 (Statista, 2024), the regions with the highest number of arrivals being Europe (707.44 million), Asia and Pacific (237.21 million) and USA (200.06 million) - Figure 1.

This huge increase in tourist traffic in recent years (excluding the Covid-19 pandemic, which in fact, after its end, stimulated people’s desire to enjoy the freedom of travel), accompanied by the tendency of tourists to visit popular destinations during peak periods of demand, are frequently considered the main reasons for excessive tourism (Żemła & Szromek, 2018).

Figure 1: Number of international tourist arrivals globally (2010-2023)

Source: Statista, <https://1511rsnss-y-https-www-statista-com.z.e-nformation.ro/statistics/209334/total-number-of-international-tourist-arrivals/>

While tourists traditionally spend their holidays in places and spaces primarily dedicated to the tourism industry, such as hotels and attractions, today they increasingly access residential spaces for accommodation. Many popular cities have thus been radically transformed by visitors, for example Venice and Dubrovnik. The rapid growth of tourism in cities such as Paris, Barcelona, and Amsterdam (Figure 2), with tourists and visitors occupying public spaces, streets and homes, has led to a negative perception of the quality of life among locals.

Figure 2: Number of international tourist arrivals in the most attractive European tourist destinations (2019-2023, in millions)

Source: Statista, <https://1511rt1cp-y-https-www-statista-com.z.e-nformation.ro/statistics/487572/leading-european-city-destinations/>

Nevertheless, the reasons for the rise in anti-tourism sentiment are much more varied. Too many visitors not only have a negative impact on the lifestyle of residents, but also affect the environment of a destination and oftentimes threaten the UNESCO World Heritage status (Seraphin, Sheeran & Pilato, 2018).

Consequently, overtourism and consumer footprint are closely interrelated, as the behaviours and decisions of individual tourists directly contribute to the environmental, social, and economic impacts of tourist destinations. The consumer footprint refers to the total social and environmental impact created by an individual through their consumption choices, including energy consumption, waste production, resource consumption, and carbon emissions. In the context of overtourism, the collective footprint of tourists exacerbates the pressure on resources and infrastructure, leading to negative consequences for destinations.

Thus, excessive tourism leads to an increase in the consumer footprint through:

- Increased carbon emissions

One of the largest contributors to a tourist’s carbon footprint is air travel. Popular destinations attract millions of international tourists, each of whom contributes significantly to greenhouse gas emissions. Frequent travel to these destinations increases total aviation emissions, a major source of global CO₂ emissions. In addition, once at their destinations, tourists use local means of transport, including buses, rental cars or taxis, which further increases the carbon footprint.

- Pressure on local resources

Overtourism puts enormous pressure on local resources, particularly water and energy. Tourists, often staying in hotels or guesthouses, use large amounts of water for showers, swimming pools, laundry and food preparation. In water-scarce regions, such as island destinations or drought-prone regions, this demand can deplete local water supplies and strain existing infrastructure. Tourist accommodation also requires energy for air conditioning, heating, lighting, and electronic devices. Large hotels and resorts catering to tourists often consume much more energy than local households, and in over-touristy destinations, this demand can contribute to energy shortages or require reliance on fossil fuels, further increasing the carbon footprint.

- Waste generation

Tourists generate significant amounts of waste, including plastic and food packaging. Many overcrowded cities and natural attractions face waste management problems as local systems struggle to Land degradation and habitat loss

Large numbers of tourists can threaten local biodiversity, especially in sensitive ecosystems such as coral reefs, rainforests, and mountain areas. The influx of visitors can disturb wildlife, damage coral reefs (through snorkelling or diving), and cause habitat fragmentation. The ecological footprint of each tourist contributes to this biodiversity loss, especially when the destination lacks sustainable tourism practices. Tourists, often unaware of their impact, stray from the beaten path, damaging sensitive ecosystems and disturbing wildlife. As visitor numbers increase, the cumulative footprint of millions of people can seriously degrade these environments. In addition, the increasing demand for more accommodation, restaurants, and entertainment facilities in over-touristed areas leads to the development of new infrastructure. This often leads to deforestation, loss of agricultural land and destruction of ecosystems, thus increasing the environmental footprint of the tourism sector.

- Cultural and social impact

In many destinations, excessive tourism leads to gentrification of neighbourhoods as tourists drive up housing costs and displace local residents. Short-term rental platforms such as Airbnb have contributed to this situation, as landlords target tourists rather than long-term residents. The influx of tourists affects the social fabric and cultural identity of the destination, as local communities are pushed aside in favour of tourism development.

At the same time, overtourism can commodify local traditions, festivals, and crafts, altering their authenticity. As tourists seek cultural experiences, local customs and practices are transformed into spectacles or commercial activities designed to satisfy consumer demand, which can lead to the erosion of culture. This socio-cultural footprint reflects how tourism alters the way of life of the host community.

- Overuse of public infrastructure

Tourism demand overwhelms public infrastructure, such as transport, health and sanitation systems. In cities that experience overtourism, the increased use of roads, public transport, and waste management systems leads to overuse and degradation. As tourists use these services, local residents may face reduced access to essential resources or services, amplifying the visitor footprint. Public spaces, from parks to markets, become crowded due to overtourism, reducing the quality of life for local residents and affecting their daily existence.

- Economic footprint and inequality

While tourism brings economic benefits, much of the revenue generated by overtourism drains away from the local economy. Large international hotel chains, tour operators and international organisations often capture a significant share of tourist spending, leaving local communities with a smaller share of the profits. This can exacerbate inequalities, especially in developing regions. Overtourism creates an economic dependency on tourism in destinations, leading to an unbalanced economy. This dependency increases the footprint, as destinations focus on increasing the number of tourists to stimulate economic growth, which leads to more construction, consumption and pressure on the environment. At the same time, the intensified tourist demand leads to a sharp increase in prices within the communities transformed into overcrowded destinations, which negatively impacts the purchasing power of the locals.

Consequently, it can be stated that overtourism negatively impacts the perception of local people on the quality of life; they even consider that their lives have deteriorated unacceptably (Goodwin, 2016). The negative perception of the effects of excessive tourism has generated rapid and violent anti-tourism movements, especially in large cities (Figure 3). This attitude has begun to be labelled in the specialized literature as tourism-phobia (Milano, Novelli & Cheer, 2019).

Figure 3: Europeans' perception of global protest movements against overtourism (August 2024)

Source: Statista, <https://1511rtkvc-y-https-www-statista-com.z.e-nformation.ro/statistics/1493484/europeans-sympathy-overtourism-protectors-worldwide/>

As observed, according to data published by Statista in August 2024, the vast majority of Europeans in cities affected by the overtourism phenomenon (65% in Germany, Spain, Sweden and France, 63% in Denmark, 57% in France and 53% in Italy) admit they support protest movements against excessive tourism, while the share of those who perceive these protests negatively is between 36% in Italy and 19% in France.

As a result, the reaction of local authorities in destinations that practice excessive tourism has been linked to the implementation of various types of restrictions (Goodwin, 2017), thus aiming either to limit the daily number of tourists (Scuttari, Isetti & Habicher, 2019), or the development of tourism infrastructure by opening new accommodation structures or by transforming residential buildings into spaces for tourist rentals (Żemła, Jaremen & Nawrocka, 2021).

According to existing data, the perception of the Europeans regarding the limitation of tourism in destinations affected by excessive tourism (Figure 4), respectively regarding the introduction of tourism taxes aimed at stopping the phenomenon (Figure 5) confirm the need to identify a balance between the benefits of tourism development and the negative effects it generates on the quality of life of residents in destinations affected by overtourism.

Figure 4: Europeans' perception of the need to limit tourism in popular destinations (August, 2024)

Source: Statista, <https://1511rtl4x-y-https-www-statista-com.z.e-nformation.ro/statistics/1493894/europeans-opinions-limiting-tourists-popular-destinations/>

In addition to strict regulations, local stakeholders have also tried to use communication tools, such as educational campaigns addressed to both citizens and visitors (Korstanje & George, 2020) and sales promotion campaigns aimed at a more equal distribution of tourist traffic in time and space (Sraphin & Yallop, 2020) by convincing tourists to visit popular destinations outside the tourist season and, respectively, by redirecting demand towards less known and visited areas.

Therefore, it is imperative to involve local authorities in identifying management strategies for tourist destinations so that the benefits are visible for both tourists and residents, the environment, and society. In this sense, the implementation of responsible tourism, which is based on strategic leadership, as well as governance based on the principles of sustainable development, are essential factors in the implementation of sustainable tourism (Mihalic & Kuscer, 2022).

Figure 5: Europeans' perception of the need to introduce a tourism tax to reduce overtourism worldwide (August, 2024)

Source: Statista, <https://1511rtl11-y-https-www-statista-com.z.e-nformation.ro/statistics/1493496/opinions-tourist-tax-fee-against-overtourism-europe/>

There is obvious complementarity between the notions of durability and sustainability, as seen by Mihalic (2016) within the SRT model, which defines the conceptual elements and the triggering factors of the implementation of sustainable tourism sustainability (Mihalic, 2016). Thus, the three components of the model refer to (Mihalic & Kuscer, 2022):

- The support capacity of the three pillars of sustainable development, namely: the economic, socio-cultural, and environmental components;
- The support capacity dictated by the socio-psychological factors that influence tourism stakeholders, namely: residents, the tourism sector, visitors;
- The support capacity determined by the socio-political factors that lead to awareness, planning, and implementation of the SRT model.

According to the World Travel & Tourism Council (WTTC), destination management to reduce overtourism should include actions such as: building a database to properly inform the tourism strategy so that all stakeholders have access to the information necessary to understand the phenomenon, establishing a tourism strategy for sustainable growth that would mitigate or prevent overcrowding and involving all stakeholders, including local communities, and establishing new financial sources to invest in infrastructure and sustainability (McKinsey and Company, 2017).

Hence, it can be said that regardless of the tactics used to substantiate sustainable destination management strategies to combat overtourism, their implementation is essential, as they aim to balance the needs of residents, visitors, and the environment.

Thus, the key strategies for sustainable management of tourist destinations can be summarized as:

- Determining the maximum number of tourists that a destination can accommodate without causing damage and using this information to set limits on the number of visitors;
- Using digital tools to monitor the number of visitors in real time, as well as online platforms to book visits to attractions with limited capacity;
- Encouraging off-season travel by applying pricing policy tools and creating special events to reduce pressure during the peak season;
- Creating sustainable accommodation facilities;
- Educating tourists on sustainable travel practices;
- Highlighting the ecological and cultural importance of the destination;
- Efficient and green-line-oriented public transport;
- Implementing waste management systems to reduce environmental damage;
- Encouraging tourists to visit lesser-known attractions to spread economic benefits and reduce overcrowding;
- Taxing tourists (e.g., tourist taxes) to fund conservation projects and local communities;
- Including local communities in decision-making to address their concerns and ensure equitable benefits;
- Encouraging the local providers to keep the economic benefits within the community.

4. Conclusions

Prioritising sustainability, climatic balance, and individual quality of life has been crucial to bringing about significant prosperity for people in this decade, when environmental and social debate has dominated international action

Destinations are being forced to reconsider their tourist strategies due to overtourism. Governments and stakeholders may guarantee a balanced relationship between tourism growth, community well-being, and environmental conservation by implementing comprehensive destination management policies. Sustainable tourism improves a destination's long-term profitability and appeal while simultaneously reducing the negative effects of overtourism.

The relationship between overtourism and consumer footprint is symbiotic, with consumption patterns and tourist behaviours amplifying the ecological, social, and economic impacts of overtourism. As millions of tourists converge towards popular destinations, their collective footprint leads to resource depletion, environmental degradation, cultural erosion, and social tensions. To mitigate these negative effects, it is essential to promote responsible tourism, in which travellers minimize their footprint through sustainable practices and destinations manage tourism more efficiently to balance economic benefits with environmental and social protection.

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